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Between process and object: NFTs and the artification of digital assets^{*}

Abstract: By bringing digital artworks to one's everyday shopping list, NFTs have revolutionized a large group's understanding of art. In this article, I challenge the stance presented by authors such as Taylor and Sloane that NFTs shift the consumption of objects to the liquid consumption of the non-material by drawing on the aesthetic identity of NFTs as images. Firstly, I analyse the evolution of blockchain products' function from that of strictly fungible tokens to non-fungible goods. NFTs rely on art's specificity and acquire their new identity by virtue of entering the art market, which does not happen with ordinary cryptocurrencies. NFTs thus benefit from the contextualization of art as a socially and technologically mediated immaterial process: they emerge as instances of the artification of a non-artistic immaterial experience and become art-like. However, an NFT as a commodity is not pure code; it does have an image attached. This distinguishes NFTs from particular fungible tokens that hold added value due to their unique historical context.

I further point out that the fact that NFTs have, as commodities, taken the form of digital images is an expression of a pervasive need for interaction with objects in today's everyday digital experience. Also, the shift of NFTs from being just "specific" phenomena as art objects to "singular" phenomena construed as authors of the ways in which they will be perceived and understood is discussed. NFTs create their own impact, on the one hand, independently of their often poor artistic or aesthetic quality, and on the other hand, as entirely dependent on their aura as mathematically and ontologically unique, visually perceptible entities.

Keywords: artification, assets, aesthetic value, art, codependency, NFTs, object, process, singularity

NFTs' development as processes

To specialists, "blockchain" means a technology for registering and disseminating identifiers of everyday processes and objects in a secure and decentralized way. Entirely digital, this technology revolutionized existing digital

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security by implementing time-stamped certificates sealed by unbreakable codes. These codes differ from commonly used passwords and other authentication methods due to their mathematical complexity, which renders them virtually undecipherable.¹

Such digital tokens are being applied in ever-wider social and economic spheres demanding trust—from assurance of goods' and services' quality (e.g., sustainable farming² or water quality management³), art authentication,⁴ and ownership certification⁵ to contracting and voting systems.⁶ Among blockchain applications, however, it is tokenized digital image collections that, beginning between 2020 and 2022, became a buzzword and hugely impacted the common perception of blockchain beyond cryptocurrencies⁷. The accessibility of NFT collections has increased the possibility for average individuals to engage with the art world as active participants through ownership of digital pieces⁸ and their consumption (e.g., in metaverses like *Otherside*). This trend has helped push art beyond the

¹ Inquiries were raised into the possibility that quantum computing might speed up processes enough to reverse the time and energy-consuming hash mining calculations that now make it impractical to try breaking the keys. Three years ago, experts warned that “given a large enough quantum computer with enough qubits, you can break elliptic curve cryptography easier than you might break RSA.” R. Huang, “Here’s why quantum computing will not break cryptocurrencies,” *Forbes*, December 10, 2021, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/rogerhuang/2020/12/21/heres-why-quantum-computing-will-not-break-cryptocurrencies> (accessed: 30.07.2024)—which means that the safest model used in traditional computing can become vulnerable with new generations of quantum computing. Today, however, the blockchain industry is embracing quantum computing in order to enhance cryptographic security. See: J. Anglen, “Exploring the convergence of blockchain and quantum computing: Pioneering secure cryptography for 2024,” *Rapid Innovation*, <https://www.rapidinnovation.io/post/exploring-convergence-blockchain-quantum-computing-secure-cryptography-2024> (accessed: 30.07.2024).

² See: DeFood, Digital Agro Exchange, <https://defood.org/>; FairFood, “Blockchain in food supply chains,” <https://fairfood.org/en/blockchain> (accessed: 25.07.2024).

³ See: R. Galarza, “Blockchain verifying and standardizing water purity,” *Water Technology*, April 22, 2022, <https://watertechonline.com/water-reuse/article/14274926/blockchain-verifying-validating-and-standardizing-water-purity> (accessed: 25.07.2024); or W. Xia, X. Chen, Ch. Song, “A framework of blockchain technology in intelligent water management,” *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 10, 2022, <https://frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2022.909606/full>.

⁴ See: Smart Verum, <https://smartverum.com> (accessed: 25.07.2024).

⁵ See: Gate2Chain, <https://gate2chain.com/trace> (accessed: 25.07.2024).

⁶ Private implementation: <https://polys.vote/#submenu:solutions>; Public implementation, see: C. Rupa et al., “Distributed-ledger-based blockchain technology for reliable electronic voting system with statistical analysis,” *Electronics* 11, 2022, 3308, <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics11203308>.

⁷ See: A.D. Popescu, “Non-fungible tokens (NFT)—innovation beyond the craze,” *Proceedings of Engineering & Technology Journal. IBEM 2021* 66 (2021).

⁸ NFT marketplaces—like OpenSea, Decentraland, Larva Labs, and Nifty Gateway NFT Marketplace, to name but a few—have populated the cybersphere and have become connected to the gaming industry, stock exchanges, and lifestyle platforms, especially in developing countries.

exclusive luxury goods market and into a space for everyday activity for vast numbers of people who previously had no interest in art.⁹

By bringing digital artworks to one's everyday shopping list—especially during the pandemic years—NFTs have also revolutionized a large group's understanding of art, and they continue to do so despite their collapse in market value¹⁰. The view on NFTs' emergence presented by authors like Taylor and Sloane is that “monetary value assigned to NFTs reflects this shift the market has taken, away from the physical, towards the commodification of the exclusively virtual and experiential. An optimistic interpretation of their rise could be that they mark a transformation from ownership consumption of objects to liquid consumption of the non-material.”¹¹ NFT collectibles indeed bear traits of conceptual art forms lacking objects, closer in nature to processes or Taylor and Sloane's “liquid” participatory experiences. Many authors emphasize the fact that the spectacular rise of NFTs has epitomized the perceptual shift from the traditional characteristic of visuality as contemplative to post-digital hyper-visuality practiced as a short look-based activity, also referred to as a “scattered gaze”: “The user's interaction with the image is quick and prevents a prolonged, rational, and critical experience that would allow him to question its origin, context, contents, or objectives. Such a ‘scattered gaze’ has been pointed out by authors such as Martín Prada.”¹² The “scattered gaze” relies on maximizing the quantity of experiences rather than their quality. This approach replaces the ordinary focus of perception—i.e., the contents or object of the experience—with the actual activity of experiencing.

The impression that we are dealing with a large-scale, decentralized, and commonplace performative experience is strengthened by NFTs' immateriality, poor quality,¹³ and ambiguity of authorship (especially in the case of the NFTs created by generative AIs).¹⁴

⁹ Some authors reflect on the NFT market critically, as one that is not liberal and decentralized (despite its technological potential to be so) but controlled by an “oligopolistic group of wealthy traders and a variety of gatekeepers who can manipulate prices.” See: B. Jenkins, “NFTs and the financialization of art,” *Cultural Studies*, March 20, 2024, pp. 1–30, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09502386.2024.2329873>.

¹⁰ See: D. Silverberg, “The NFT market hasn't recovered. but they're still bullish on the tech,” *Fast Company*, November 1, 2024, <https://www.fastcompany.com/91007939/the-nft-market-still-hasnt-recovered-but-theyre-still-bullish-on-the-tech> (accessed: 2.08.2024).

¹¹ J. Taylor, K. Sloane, “Art markets without art, art without objects,” *The Garage Journal: Studies in Art, Museums and Culture* 2021, no. 2, pp. 152–175, <https://doi.org/10.35074/GJ.2021.97.81.008>.

¹² L.D. Rivero-Moreno, “Blockchain culture and digital image precariousness. Questioning NFTs as an art preservation strategy,” *Artnodes* 33, 2024, p. 3, <https://doi.org/10.7238/artnodes.v0i33.416449>. See also: *Art, Images and Network Culture*, ed. M. Prada, Seville 2021, pp. 233–236, https://www.juanmartinprada.net/textos/Juan_Martin_Prada_BOOK_ART_IMAGES_AND_NETWORK_CULTURE.pdf.

¹³ Ibid.

¹⁴ See: A. Tuğan, “Liberation of the medium: Decentralization of dynamic generative art creations by NFT marketplaces,” [in:] *Proceedings of the XXIV Generative Art Conference*, 2021, pp. 409–420.

One can, of course, debate the immateriality of the NFTs insofar as all digitally mediated objects of perception are embodied in their physical devices and rely on the receivers' embodied perception. However, construed as an object of ownership or a commodity, NFTs most certainly ought to be interpreted differently from, e.g., a physical painting or sculpture. Firstly, their perceptual existence is not identical to the devices in which they are quasi-embodied. These devices operate only as temporary and not exclusive display systems, in which NFTs do not differ so much from ordinary digital images, film, or music. Secondly, their identity as unique objects becomes blurred or debatable when you take into account the fact that their apparitions—i.e., the actual object of perception of the one and unique NFT—are, in fact, multiple digital instantiations or events that have their own place (a device) and time of existence and, therefore, become multiplied, unlike physical objects.¹⁵ In other words, every time I look at my one and unique Bored Ape whose original file is stored under lock and (cryptographic) key as code, its image is, in fact, created on my screen from the data stored in the block, just like any other digital image is, by the displaying rows of pixels by an app, every time in a new perceptible form. Despite being based on the same mathematical code, it will be slightly different from the previous time I looked, depending on the type of display, the settings of my display, the size of the displayed instantiation, etc. This is more the case with 3D visual files (of sculptures, buildings, natural spaces) displayed through VR goggles: there are even more instantiations of displaying the same coded set of images, as the whole technology is aimed at a mimetic recreation of the natural experience, which is multi-faceted and experientially diverse. In VR, similar to simple jpg presentations on screens, this is attained through real-time creation of images, every time from scratch. Their perceptual presentation is a process whose effects depend on the devices used.

Another factor differentiating NFTs—as processes rather than objects—from ordinary commodities is their entanglement in the social contract between celebrity influencers and their followers, which has helped raise NFTs to the status of commodities. The cryptocurrency-based asset market could have been growing at its own economically regulated rate if not for the sudden interest of media celebrities—showmen, artists, business tycoons, athletes, etc.—in its visual segment (NFTs), followed by their fandom. The celebration of social media audiences following of new NFT collection releases and purchases by these celebrities became a ritual or a mass happening in itself. Perhaps aided

¹⁵ Authors note also that there is a disconnect between the actual timestamp (the digital token) and the image it corresponds to. Some claim that it robs the original of its Benjaminian “aura” of authenticity. See: A. Notaro, “All that is solid melts in the Ethereum: The brave new (art) world of NFTs,” *Journal of Visual Art Practice* 21, 2022, no. 4, pp. 359–382, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14702029.2022.2129204>.

by the coincidence with lockdowns, it involved crowds in an active art-market performance without which the NFTs might not have acquired the momentum they did.¹⁶

Quite apart from participation in the celebrity-driven market ritual, the activities involved with the mere acquiring of an NFT also constitute a processual experience evocative of participation in conceptual performances. In most cases, to own cryptocurrencies, one needs to know how to (safely) operate on exchange platforms, create secure wallets, connect them to selected marketplaces, learn how to bid, how to execute transactions, and finally, how to access the purchased tokens without losing or having stolen one's codes. Even if more and more people are becoming familiar and confident with it, this complex process demands knowledge, a certain amount of technological "wizardry," and contextualized social interaction.¹⁷

Having laid out the aforementioned assessment of the NFT phenomenon as process-based rather than object-based, I will first investigate this stance more in-depth and then challenge it by drawing on the ontological and aesthetic identity of NFTs as tokens and as images.

NFT as an artified process

The evolution of blockchain-based products has moved from strictly fungible tokens used and treated as currencies¹⁸ to non-fungible ones, which have become assets. When used and regarded as fungible tokens, cryptocurrencies themselves pose interesting questions concerning their identity: (a) can they be treated as fiat currencies, (b) do they have backing in other assets, or (c) do they have an intrinsic value like commodity currencies?

¹⁶ See: A.A. Mehr, A. Shahim, "NFTs and the art world: Understanding the role of social media in the emergence of digital collections," *British Journal of Arts and Humanities* 5, 2023, no. 6, pp. 277–290, <https://doi.org/10.34104/bjah.02302770290>.

¹⁷ Some authors emphasize also the relationality of the NFT market, as an added value. Experiments including the creation of blockchain-based metaverses have been spurred in order to measure the potential of NFTs in building social interaction. See: B. Carraro, F. Pola, A. Sanna, "NFT between technology, art and neurosciences: A multidisciplinary approach," [in:] *Computer & Media Art at the Age of Metaverses and NFT, Proceedings of the 7th Computer Art Congress (CAC7)*, eds. K. Zreik, M. Veyrat, M. Quiniou, Paris 2023, pp. 37–54.

¹⁸ The status of cryptocurrencies has been subject to legal debate for several years, due to many factors, like value volatility and lack of regulations regarding them. In early 2024, the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) issued regulations for cryptocurrencies that define them as securities rather than currencies. Cf. A. Hayes, "How SEC regs will change cryptocurrency markets," Investopedia, July 24, 2024, <https://www.investopedia.com/news/how-sec-regs-will-change-cryptocurrency-markets/> (accessed: 31.07.2024). This, however, does not have bearing on our argumentation.

Regarding (a): Despite the apparent distance and a revolutionary break from traditional fiat currencies, cryptocurrencies, in fact, rely on a shared social contract of trust in blockchain technology and its mechanics of scarcity that guarantee the cryptocurrencies their value. This trust is similar or alternative to the state warranties of value of traditional currencies. Regarding (b): There are “stablecoins” backed by fiat currencies or other assets, but most cryptocurrencies are not “representative” (i.e., backed by assets). Regarding (c): This is the most intriguing question about blockchain-based fungible tokens. A simple reply would, of course, be “no.” How could cryptocurrencies have any intrinsic value if they do not have any material form and are, by decree, identical and interchangeable: fungible, just like cheap, aluminium-minted fiat currency coins? However, the source of the market value of cryptocurrencies lies in their very definition and actual form or structure: in the sophisticated mathematical code that they are. That code—and not something external concerning the fungible tokens—makes them so rare, scarce (the number of, e.g., Bitcoins is finite, albeit huge), and obtainable only with a tremendous amount of work and energy.¹⁹ These features are an intrinsic factor of the value of each cryptocurrency unit.

This intrinsic value of fungible tokens informs the development of non-fungible tokens (notwithstanding the legal and regulatory circumstances). Both fungible and non-fungible tokens’ value depends on their unique timestamp that literally freezes the virtual flux of code and solidifies them into unchangeable digital entities. In fact, a fungible token could be minted as a non-fungible one. From the ontological perspective, every token minted on a blockchain is already a unique and unalterable event—timestamped and registered on a block—that is thus slightly differentiated from all others, although it is identical in form. An issuance of Bitcoin or Ethereum could potentially be used not as a currency unit but, from the beginning or a certain point onward, as a commodity—like with SFTs²⁰—and become a celebrated NFT, a collectible. It would not behave like all other Bitcoins, i.e., it would not be just an issuance of value, fractionable

¹⁹ The change of protocol from proof-of-work (PoW) to proof-of-stake (PoS) on the Ethereum blockchain and its use by newer chains significantly reduces the energy needed for the minting process. Bitcoin continues with PoW. See: A. Bubenko, “PoW vs PoS: A comparison of two popular blockchain consensus mechanisms,” Morpher, January 3, 2024, <https://www.morpher.com/blog/pow-vs-pos-comparison> (accessed: 1.08.2024).

²⁰ Obviously, this is more theoretical than practical, as the common consensus around cryptocurrencies has been that they are interchangeable and fractionable. Also, from a technological point of view, for many years, there have been two separate coding standards for fungible and non-fungible tokens. Today, however, SFT (semi-fungible tokens) are also available. “They are a combination of both asset classes and provide more flexibility and functionality. A semi-fungible token exists first as a fungible token, which can be exchanged with similar tokens in its class. They only change into non-fungible tokens with distinct values when used.” See: “Non-fungible tokens (NFTs) vs semi-fungible tokens (SFTs): Explained,” KuCoin Learn, June 26, 2024, <https://www.kucoin.com/pl/learn/web3/non-fungible-token-nft-vs-semi-fungible-token-sft> (accessed: 11.08.2024).

and exchangeable, that still has the form of a Bitcoin or Ethereum, with a value changing according to its popularity, like any other asset. It would be similar to certain fiat currency coins minted for a special occasion, which shifts their value from fiat to commodity money. Like minting a special physical fiat currency coin in silver, specific crypto-fungible tokens could be minted as non-fungible (or as SFTs) by inserting an additional line of code.

What actually happened is slightly different, though. The NFTs that succeeded as collectibles and differentiated themselves from ordinary cryptocurrencies, acquired their new identity by virtue of entering the art market and not through their own intrinsic capacity to build abstract, mathematical forms of pure code. Already in 2012, in her article “Overview of Colored Coins,” promoting the idea of creating NFTs, Meni Rosenfeld proposed adding a *visual* feature to certain coins in order to shift them from being fungible to non-fungible.²¹ The main category pointed out by her and other creators of NFTs as granting their uniqueness and originality—in contrast to fungible tokens—is not more code, however unique it might be, but a perceptible detail added to the token. Here is the tricky part of this logic that I would like to point out. In fact, that visual detail is also a line of code that forms a sensorially perceptible entity. From the programming point of view, it is as repeatable and copyable as any other line of code. There is nothing essentially *singular* about them once they have been created. A perceptible feature, e.g., an image by Beeple, minted as an NFT on June 1, 2022, could be used again in its identical form as code and minted as a second NFT on June 2, 2022.²² What would differentiate them is, in fact, the blockchain-guaranteed timestamp and not the perceptible code attached to them. This means that the consensus on using perceptible attachments to tokens in order to differentiate them from fungible ones is in itself insufficient—the uniqueness of an NFT depends as much on marking it with a perceptible feature, e.g., an image (i.e., code that displays such a feature) as on the event of stamping one at a particular time. In any case, the choice of the crypto-token world was for codes with sensorially perceptible effects and not some other ones.

²¹ See: M. Rosenfeld, “Overview of colored coins,” Allquantor, December 4, 2012, <https://allquantor.at/blockchainbib/pdf/rosenfeld2012overview.pdf> (accessed: 29.07.2024). Her idea was in essence similar to SFTs: “They can be exchanged for other colored coins or uncolored bitcoins in a single atomic transaction—meaning there is no counterparty risk, even without blockchain confirmations. And once again the entire range of scripting options is available to allow more complex trades, such as exchanging for coins of a different blockchain with a similar security guarantee, or automated escrow.”

²² This practice is legal and done not only in open NFT editions but also in limited NFT editions. It impacts the value of the NFTs and depends on individual NFT minter’s sales strategy. See: “Can there be multiple NFTs for one piece of digital art?,” NFT Plazas, <https://nftplazas.com/learn-about-nfts/multiple-nfts-for-one-piece-of-digital-art/> (accessed: 4.08.2024).

This arbitrary choice, i.e., for the addition of a sensorially perceptible detail—first colour, then memes, then all sorts of images, films, 3D, and audible file collections—has shifted their originality to the specificity²³ of the art world. In my view, NFTs thus started not only benefitting from the contextualization of art as a socially and technologically mediated immaterial process²⁴ but also as instances of the *artification* of a non-artistic immaterial experience that becomes art-like.²⁵ To support this view, let me look into the problem with the original aesthetic ideas that inform the concept of *artification* as reference.

As proposed by Yuriko Saito and Ossi Naukkarinen in the 2012 volume of *Contemporary Aesthetics* dedicated to this concept transferred from Finnish philosophy, this term denotes processes of *transformation* of an object, activity, or phenomenon from its native context (e.g., industry, services, education) and function (e.g., providing goods, servicing, or instructing) to that of the art world.²⁶ Such processes rely to a large extent on aestheticization. According to Yuriko Saito, they also promulgate creativity, innovation, and the cult of individual authorship as crucial elements of artification.²⁷ As demonstrated earlier, the introduction of image-based (or audible file-based) NFTs to blockchain technology applications certainly bears traits of aestheticization and innovation: cryptocurrencies, smart contracts, and ordinary blockchain-based certificates are devoid of aesthetic stimuli, while collections of images and music files are sensually perceptible and thus aesthetically potent. Connecting typical digital files to blockchain code was considered so innovative and revolutionary that it quickly caught the attention of market opportunists. Uniqueness added to otherwise mundane pieces of code imbued them with the charm of an artistic aura in both ways: a blockchain code became unique due to an image attached to it, while an otherwise ordinary (multiplicable) visual (or aural, video, etc.) file became unique through the blockchain time-stamping process.

²³ The concept of specificity is understood here as in: J. Koestlé-Cate, “Singularity and specificity: Writing on art,” *Journal of Writing in Creative Practice* 5, no. 1, 2012, pp. 107–123, https://doi.org/10.1386/jwcp.5.1.107_1.

²⁴ About immaterial processes, see: A. Łukaszewicz, J. Petri, “Reshaping aesthetics and aesthetic sensibility in a hybrid environment,” *Contemporary Aesthetics* s10, 2022, art. 7, <https://www.contempaesthetics.org/hybrid-aesthetics.pdf> (accessed: 3.08.2024).

²⁵ On artification, see: A. Erjavec, “Artification and the aesthetic regime of art,” *Contemporary Aesthetics* s4, 2012, art. 8, https://digitalcommons.risd.edu/liberalarts_contempaesthetics/vol0/iss4/8/ (accessed: 3.08.2024).

²⁶ See: O. Naukkarinen, Y. Saito, “Introduction,” *Contemporary Aesthetics* s4, 2012, art. 1, https://digitalcommons.risd.edu/liberalarts_contempaesthetics/vol0/iss4/1/ (accessed: 3.08.2024).

²⁷ Saito, in her paper, proposed a critical view of the artification of everyday practices based on the dangers of over-individualistic leadership emulating the artistic genius; the lack of standards in studies taken up by creativity; and the devaluation of high-art aesthetic experience in view of a dilution of aesthetic experience brought in excess to everyday processes, especially in the workplace. Cf. Y. Saito, “Everyday aesthetics and artification,” *Contemporary Aesthetics* s4, 2012, art. 5, https://digitalcommons.risd.edu/liberalarts_contempaesthetics/vol0/iss4/5 (accessed: 4.08.2024).

Creativity and individual authorship in the context of NFTs may remain debatable for reasons mentioned above, i.e., the ever more popular mechanical production and banality of tokenized objects (both digital and physical). However, what such tokenized files lack in craftsmanship, artistry, or taste, blockchain as a system in itself supplies to the ultimate product (an artified NFT) due to its complexity and mystery.

Roberta Shapiro recently returned to the concept of artification by placing it in the sociological context as a complex process: “[A]rtification emerges not as a linear development but as a composite process, the cumulative result of concurrent trends that may be met by obstacles and contrary developments. Artification also progresses contemporaneously with other trends such as sportification, commercialisation and so on, whose advocates may alternatively compete or collaborate.”²⁸ I would add “gamification” and “ethicization”²⁹ to the list—two trends that seem to be taking over and transforming ever more spheres of social interaction—including blockchain. In her article, which I consider a methodological foundation for a theory of artification, Shapiro proposes 10 micro-processes that form the complex phenomenon of artification: “The most salient constituent processes of artification [...] are: displacement, renaming, shifting categories, organisational and institutional change, functional differentiation, redefining time, legal consolidation, patronage, aesthetic formalisation, and intellectualisation.”³⁰ Several of these microprocesses are characteristic of the NFT socio-economic art-like movement and are interconnected in a causative manner: the aesthetic enrichment (addition of perceptible objects to pure code) of NFTs has induced an institutional change: the creation of *crypto art* markets instead of general crypto asset markets. The apparent intellectualization of the asset purchase processes—a buyer needs to be more tech-savvy to purchase an NFT image than to buy stock, bonds, land, or gold—has added to the displacement of the context from that of the “common” to that of the “enlightened,” even though an image of a Bored Ape in itself would not have inspired this kind of value displacement if it were sold in its more natural place (e.g., a t-shirt distributed as an ad for a yacht club in a seaside resort).

²⁸ R. Shapiro, “Artification as process,” *Cultural Sociology* 13, 2019, no. 3, pp. 265–275, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1749975519854955>.

²⁹ Blockchain as a whole—especially as a decentralized ledger system—has been considered, from the beginning, a particularly beneficial innovation from the social justice and ethics point of view, as an almost utopian, aestheticized, new reality of social interaction. See: N. Atanasova, “The aestheticization of relations within the blockchain,” [in:] *Гуманитарные знания в XXI веке: вызовы, ценности, перспективы шестые арэфьевские чтения*, Москва 2023, pp. 238–253.

³⁰ R. Shapiro, “Artification as process.”

In the same aforementioned volume of *Contemporary Aesthetics*, Larry Shiner³¹ elaborates on three types of artification processes—decoration, transformation, and modification—that seem to inform the NFTs market even more clearly. *Transformation*, according to him, “refers to a process in which something not initially understood to be art is subsequently recognised as belonging to the realm of art”³²—in other words, it is engulfed by the widespread understanding of the art world through its institutional theory, in Dickie’s sense. This is not entirely the kind of artification we are dealing with here because if it were so, tokens (like coins) that are not connected with any specific visually or audibly perceptible files could be considered as “art” (i.e., a commodity and not currency). However, I think that the case of the NFTs may be considered an example of artification construed as *modification* because, through acquiring aesthetically meaningful elements, they managed to insert themselves into the market, where they relied on mechanisms pertaining specifically to the art market. The NFT marketplace has thus become art-like. The most robust case for artification in the context of the NFT phenomenon is, in my view, for *blockchain itself* (and not its products, the NFTs) through the third sense of artification proposed by Shiner, i.e., *decoration*. As explained earlier, in itself, blockchain structures (tokens of various types) that rely on code only—and thus are immaterial and “formless”—have proved to be insufficient to induce aesthetic enchantment in their original and new users.³³ It was only after the insertion of additional objects (files with apparent aesthetic qualities) that the whole sphere of crypto-trading acquired the status of the art market.³⁴

NFTs as perceptible objects

Thus, the fact that an NFT as a commodity is not pure code but has an image, a video, a VR, or a music file attached—and is identified with it rather

³¹ L. Shiner, “Artification, fine art, and the myth of ‘the artist’,” *Contemporary Aesthetics* s4, 2012, art. 4, https://digitalcommons.risd.edu/liberalarts_contempaesthetics/vol0/iss4/4 (accessed: 4.08.2024).

³² Ibid.

³³ It’s true that there is a long history of analysing computer code itself through the lens of aesthetic concepts like that of “form.” See, e.g., many of the texts in *Aesthetic Computing*, ed. A.P. Fishwick, Cambridge 2006. However, any artistic or aesthetic properties to be found within blockchain code will be visible only to the minuscule number of persons directly involved in its programming, not to the vastly larger group of its end users.

³⁴ One frequently analysed example of artification processes of an entire sector of business that will further develop and greatly benefit from NFTs is the fashion industry, especially its digital versions in the metaverse. See: G. Murtas, G. Pedeliento, F. Mangiò, “Luxury fashion brands at the gates of the web 3.0: An analysis of early experimentations with NFTs and the metaverse,” *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing* 15, 2024, no. 1, pp. 90–114, <https://doi.org/10.1080/20932685.2023.2249476>.

than with the code behind it—is fundamental for its status as a specific artistic asset. Indeed, we all agree that to their typical consumers, NFTs are images with a unique code attached, while for blockchain programmers, they are special types of code enriched by a perceptual element (notwithstanding the fact that it is still reducible to more code, as was mentioned earlier). The latter distinguishes NFTs both from ordinary cryptocurrencies (which are entirely fungible and pure code) and from other non-fungible tokens that hold added value due to their unique historical context, like SFTs.

We can interpret the above-mentioned artification of NFTs as commodities in the form of digital sensorially perceptible forms as an expression of a pervasive need for interaction with *objects* rather than *processes* in today's everyday digital experience. As objects of perception, ownership, retention of value, social identification (i.e., owners recognizing themselves as members of the global NFTs community), legal regulations, etc., they have, in a scattered network of nodes, *stopped* the digital flux and became foci of stability, immutable pivots around which everything else that is digital rotates and flows. I would call this influence on the perception of the digital realm *grounding*: following the universal trend for mindfulness, slow life, and connectedness with the immediate local environment.³⁵

Let us look at the following two aspects of this interpretation: 1. the personalization of the digital environment for everyday living, and 2. the shift of NFTs from being just “specific” phenomena as art objects to “singular” phenomena within the art world.

With regard to the first problem, I will begin by pointing out that the user and consumer of NFTs as art objects engage, in fact, with NFTs' non-interchangeability amidst the multitude of interchangeable digital imagery. The economic value of NFTs relies on their personal value, which is due not to their aesthetic qualities but to the fact that out of a thousand copies of a particular image, this one particular copy that I own is “an original” because it has a timestamp and ownership certificate attached. This original digital entity thus acquires an ontological identity that renders it *like* a physical object. We have long assumed that only *res extensa* can distinguish between separate individual entities of the same form. In contrast, digital entities have been considered mathematically identical and ubiquitous and, thus, in their identity, closer to forms than to substances, if we may

³⁵ Many of these theories link groundedness with sustainability, a concept very much in line with the transformation of blockchain in the recent years to more carbon-footprint-conscious models. See: T. Ericson, B.G. Kjønstad, A. Barstad, “Mindfulness and sustainability,” *Ecological Economics* 104, 2014, pp. 73–79, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2014.04.007> and G. Carrus, A. Panno, “Mindfulness as a path towards sustainable lifestyle change, resilience, and well-being: Community, social, and environmental factors,” [in:] *Enhancing Resilience in Youth*, eds. Ch. Steinebach, Á. Langer, Cham 2019, pp. 105–114, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-25513-8_7.

continue applying handy Aristotelian terminology.³⁶ An NFT behaves in our everyday experience like a private personal teddy bear that may originally have been identical to several thousand other identical-looking teddy bears but which—because we have the right of ownership to this particular one—is different from the rest of them and is our personal teddy bear.

What NFTs do here, however, is also introduce an interesting relation between *ownership* and *possession*. In ordinary, physical experience, our teddy bear becomes different from all other ones because, as its owner, we have possessed this one for such a long time that it became a bearer not only of our fond memories but also of unique wear and tear caused by years of adventures. From this point of view, an NFT is only “owned” and not “possessed,” as it will never alter its digital form. What is possessed is a plethora of instantiations (images or copies of our NFT on various devices) that are, in their form, identical to the one and only original that we own. The personal aspect here is that without possessing it, we know that despite many identical images representing our NFTs, only one is our own and unique (we legally own it)—while all other ones are nobody’s and, by consensus, never will belong to anyone. In a way, this new form of ownership extends our personal connection to all of them.³⁷

Concerning the second point of the two introduced at the beginning of this passus, I would like to note that the mechanism described above is a real game-changer for this cluster of the art world. NFTs as objects are *specifically* art-like, a status they have acquired through *artification*. But their nature in this regard is, in my view, more than *specific*; it is also *singular*. Here is the difference between the two concepts explained by Koestlé-Cate: “Specificity infers a context-directed situation, wherein an artwork accommodates itself to the specifics of a particular place (as in site-specific work), singularity denotes an art-directed situation, whereby the context accommodates itself to the work of art.”³⁸ Singular objects here are construed as agents responsible for a transformation of a context that retroactively affects them. They are authors of the ways in which they will be perceived and understood; a singularity “denotes a model whereby a cultural object, event or situation creates its own conditions of recep-

³⁶ I am ignoring the fact that in their structure, digital entities are also reducible to binary electric processes and hence are mini-performances rather than objects. Firstly, they present themselves as if they were perceptible macro-objects; and secondly, we can argue that physical objects are similarly reducible to binary processes of quanta of energy that present themselves in a tangible form. The difference between them can be considered merely quantitative and not qualitative.

³⁷ As suggested earlier, one could mint a second NFT with the same perceptible file attached, and by virtue of a timestamp on it, it becomes a new NFT. There can be a limited or unlimited number of such “originals.” We are talking here about the relation between the original timestamped one and its ordinary non-timestamped copies.

³⁸ J. Koestlé-Cate, “Singularity and specificity,” p. 109.

tion and establishes its own interpretative frameworks.”³⁹ As singularities, NFTs create their own impact, on the one hand, as independent of their often poor artistic or aesthetic quality,⁴⁰ and, on the other hand, as entirely dependent on their *aura* as mathematically and ontologically unique, visually perceptible entities. I would argue that it is this complex codependence that makes NFTs *singular*: the perceptible object’s originality is heteronomous, as it depends on the timestamp on the blockchain (and not on its intrinsic form), and the blockchain token’s participation in the art market is heteronomous, as it depends on the attachment of an aesthetically perceptible object (and not on its intrinsic code form). Together, this codependent duo, known as an NFT, has created conditions of its reception independently of market regulators, lawmakers, art critics, galleries, and museums.⁴¹

Concluding remarks

The insights expressed above are intended to draw the reader’s attention to the fact that, contrary to the popular understanding of the NFTs as a simple fad for a stylized type of visuals, they are, in fact, a complex and dynamic phenomenon that links its ontological structure to its financial and social value. This ontological structure relies on blockchain technology’s guarantee of uniqueness and—simultaneously—on the perceptible character of the asset. Demonstrated processes of artification and internal codependence, which bring the digital sphere closer to our habitual modes of operating drawn from the physical realm, may be helpful models for understanding future digitally mediated everyday practices that will likely emerge in the coming decades. The example of the processes originated by NFTs may especially inform all of the new spheres where blockchain tokenization will substitute the traditional archiving of events, certification of quality, authentication of identity, and transfer of items. In each of

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ For critiques of the aesthetic quality of such products, see: W. Welsch, “A big disenchantment,” *Contemporary Aesthetics* 10, 2022, art. 8, <https://contempaesthetics.org/2022/11/29/a-big-disenchantment/> (accessed: 3.08.2024).

⁴¹ I distinguish typical NFT products, based on digital works attached to blockchain certificates, from tokenized physical art pieces. The latter do not partake in the artification process of blockchain and are not singular. They are just a tool for securing artists’ rights to gains from resales, while serving as authentication for original physical works of art. Auctions of tokenized physical works are a different and complex topic, involving a relationship between the historical original and its digital 3D scan attached to the token. See: F. Tuszko, M. Lewicki, “Taming liquidity: The relation between materiality and the value of artworks on the example of Polish NFT auctions,” *View. Theories and Practices of Visual Culture* 34, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.36854/widok/2022.34.2627>.

these cases, we may encounter similar entanglements that alter these processes and render them codependent on coding. Thus, the authentication of identity may be replaced by redefining it. Archiving may become redistribution. The transfer may become transferless attribution. We may need to learn quickly to adapt to all these effects of blockchain's codependence.

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